

Novelty as a Measure of Interestingness in Knowledge Discovery

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Abstract— Rule Discovery is an important technique for mining knowledge from large databases. Use of objective measures for discovering interesting rules leads to another data mining problem, although of reduced complexity. Data mining researchers have studied subjective measures of interestingness to reduce the volume of discovered rules to ultimately improve the overall efficiency of KDD process.

In this paper we study *novelty* of the discovered rules as a subjective measure of interestingness. We propose a hybrid approach based on both objective and subjective measures to quantify *novelty* of the discovered rules in terms of their deviations from the known rules (knowledge). We analyze the types of deviation that can arise between two rules and categorize the discovered rules according to the user specified threshold. We implement the proposed framework and experiment with some public datasets. The experimental results are promising.

Keywords— Knowledge Discovery in Databases (KDD), Interestingness, Subjective Measures, Novelty Index.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE vast search space of hidden patterns in the massive databases is a challenge for the KDD community. For example, in a database with n distinct items, the number of potential frequent item sets is exponential in n . In a database with n records, the potential number of clusters is $\frac{1}{k!} \sum_{i=1}^k (-1)^{k-i} \binom{k}{i} (i)^n$ [6]. However, a vast majority of

these patterns are pruned by the score functions engaged in the mining algorithm. To avoid computing the score function for the entire search space, optimization strategies are used. For example, in association rule mining, confidence is the commonly used score function and the anti-monotonic property of frequent itemsets is the optimization strategy.

Despite massive reduction of search space by employing suitable score function and optimization strategies, all of the discovered patterns are not useful for the users. Consequently, researchers have been strongly motivated to further restrict the search space, by supplying constraints to the data mining

algorithm [5] and providing good measures of interestingness [9,18].

Constraints based mining techniques allow the users to specify the rules to be discovered according to their background knowledge, thereby making the KDD process more effective [5,10]. A complicated mining query can be used to express constraints specified by the user in order to make the mining process more efficient [22,23,24,25,26].

There are two types of interestingness measures that have been studied in data mining literature viz. Objective and Subjective measures. Objective measures are based on the statistical significance (certainty, coverage, etc.) or structure (simplicity) of the patterns [7,10]. Subjective measures are based on the end-user who evaluates the patterns on the basis of novelty, actionability and unexpectedness, etc. [2,3,4,9,12,13].

In real life KDD endeavors, it is often required to compare the rules mined from datasets generated under different contexts (for example, at different points in time or in two different locations). Unless the underlying data generation process has changed dramatically, it is expected that the rules discovered from one set are likely to be similar (in varying degrees) to those discovered from another set. Some of the discovered rules may be identical to the known rules, some may be generalization/ specialization of the known rules and some others may be same or different with varying degrees of sameness/difference.

As the number of rules discovered by data mining algorithms becomes huge, the time consumed and the space required for maintaining and understanding these rules becomes vast. *Novelty* of a rule can be used as an effective way to filter the rule set discovered from the target data set thereby, reducing the volume of the output.

Novelty is defined as the extent to which the discovered rules contribute to new knowledge [1,2,3]. In this paper we focus on the quantification of *novelty* and use this measure for categorization of discovered rules. Though *novelty* is a subjective measure, we propose a strategy to quantify objectively the *novelty index* of each discovered rule, and facilitate categorization of rules based on the degree of novelty desired by the user. Asking the user to specify a threshold to filter rules of desired degree of novelty, captures user subjectivity.

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II. RELATED WORK

There are many proposals that have studied the novelty in disciplines such as robotics, machine learning and statistical outliers detection [14,15,16,17]. Generally, these methods build a model of training set that is selected to contain no examples of the important (i.e. novel) class [11]. Subsequently, the mechanisms detect the deviation from this model by some way. For instance, Kohonen and Oja proposed a novelty filter, which is based on computing the bit-wise difference between the current input and the closest match in the training set [11]. In [21], a sample application of applying association rule learning is presented. By monitoring the variance of the confidence of particular rules inferred from the association rule learning on training data, it provides information on the difference of such parameters before and after the testing data entering the system. Hence, with some pre-defined threshold, abnormalities can be fairly detected.

The techniques that have been proposed in statistical literature are focused on modeling the support of the dataset and then detecting inputs that don't belong to that support. The choice of whether to use statistical methods or machine learning methods is based on the data, the application, and the domain knowledge [14].

To our knowledge no concrete work has been conducted to tackle the novelty measure in data mining. The work proposed in [8] detects the novelty of rules mined from text [8]. In this work, the novelty is estimated based on the lexical knowledge in WordNet. The proposed approach defines a measure of semantic distance between two words in WordNet and determined by the length of the shortest path between the two words (w_i, w_j) . The novelty is defined as the average of this distance across all pairs of the words (w_i, w_j) , where w_i is a word in the antecedent and w_j is a word in the consequent.

In [2], a framework has been proposed to quantify novelty in terms of computing the deviation of currently discovered knowledge with respect to domain knowledge and previously discovered knowledge. The approach presented in [2] is intuitive in nature and lays more emphasis on user involvement in quantification process by way of parameter specification. In the present work, the quantification is performed objectively and user involvement is sought for categorization of rules based on *novelty index*.

III. NOVELTY INDEX

Let D_i denote the database extension at time t_i , and K_i denote the knowledge discovered from D_i . Figure 1 shows the knowledge discovered at two time instances. Major volume of K_{i+1} would be the overlapping region that represents previously discovered knowledge. The shaded portion denotes the novel knowledge. Thus the rules falling in the shaded area are assigned high degree of *novelty* compared to those in the overlapping regions.

The proposed framework assigns a *novelty index* to each discovered rule that indicates its proximity/deviation from some existing rule in the rule base of previously discovered

knowledge.

Figure 1. Regions of Discovered Rules

Novelty index of a rule is the deviation with respect to a given rule set. It is a pair (\check{A}, \check{C}) that indicates the deviation of the antecedent and consequent of the rule with those of the closest rule in the previously discovered knowledge. To compute the *novelty index* of a rule, the deviation is measured for the antecedent and the consequent at conjunct level and subsequently the conjunct level deviation is combined to compute rule level deviation.

A. Definitions and Notations

A rule R has the form: $A \rightarrow C$ where A denotes an antecedent and C denotes a consequent. Both A and C are in CNF $(c_1 \wedge c_2 \wedge \dots \wedge c_k)$. The conjunct c_j is of the form $\langle \check{A}, O, V \rangle$. Where \check{A} is an attribute, $Dom(\check{A})$ is the domain of \check{A} , and $V \in Dom(\check{A})$, $O \in \{=, <, >, \geq, \leq\}$. Without loss of generality, we consider both A and C as sets of conjuncts for further processing.

B. Deviation at Conjunct Level

In order to quantify deviation between any two conjuncts, the attributes, operators, and attribute values of the two conjuncts in question need to be taken into account.

Definition 3.1 Two conjuncts c_i and c_j $\langle \check{A}_i O_i V_i \rangle$ and $\langle \check{A}_j O_j V_j \rangle$ respectively) are compatible if and only if $\check{A}_i = \check{A}_j$. Otherwise, we consider c_i and c_j as non-compatible.

Definition 3.2 Let c_i and c_j be two non-compatible conjuncts. The deviation $\delta(c_i, c_j)$ between them is defined to be 1.

We capture the following four types of deviations between two compatible conjuncts.

- **Z-deviation:** This type signifies identical conjuncts and is quantified by numeric 0.
- **V-deviation:** This type of deviation signifies the magnitude of change in the value of the attribute in two conjuncts. In order to normalize, we quantify this type of deviation as the ratio of the change to the range of the attribute value.

This method of computation of V-deviation is suitable for only numeric and ordinal attributes. In case of nominal attributes, the change in value can be quantified in terms of probabilities. Since ordinal domains generally have small and manageable cardinality, prior domain knowledge can be used to assign probabilities to domain values. In case it is not feasible to assign probabilities in the above-mentioned way (e.g. color of car), the dataset itself can be used to

compute probabilities corresponding to each domain value.

- **C-deviation:** This type of deviation signifies the deviation in the conditional operators in the two conjuncts. In order to quantify C-deviation, we take into account the type of change in the condition. The operators are formatted on a number line as shown in Figure 2. The deviation between the operators is quantified by the distance between the operators on the numberline.

We define a function $opdist (O_1, O_2) \rightarrow \{0,1,2,3,4\}$, which denotes the distance between the two distinct operators (O_1, O_2) on the numberline. We define four possible values of deviations (0, 1/5, 2/5, 3/5, 4/5) between any two operators, ranking the extent of deviation between condition operators in two conjuncts.

Figure 2. Operators on Numberline

- **CV-deviation:** Quantifies V-deviation in presence of C-deviation. It captures the co-occurrence of change in both conditions and attribute values in two conjuncts.

We compute the C-deviation (c) and V-deviation (v) independently of each other, in the two given conjuncts. The user defines a real valued function $f(c,v) \rightarrow [0,1]$ to combine the two types of deviations. Depending on the importance of the type of deviations for a specific application in a domain, different functions can be used for computing deviations on different attributes.

Typically, $f(c,v)$ is of the form w_1c+w_2v , where $w_1+w_2=1$.

Note that, the computation of deviation between two conjuncts is objective in all types of deviation, except CV-deviation, where the user subjectivity is captured. Depending on the importance of either C or V deviation, the user assigns appropriate weights w_1 and w_2 .

The following definition formalizes the quantification of Conjunct level deviation.

Definition 3.3 Let c_1 and c_2 be two compatible conjuncts ($\langle A_1O_1V_1 \rangle$ and $\langle A_2O_2V_2 \rangle$ respectively). The deviation of c_1 with respect to c_2 is defined as follows:

$$\delta(c_1, c_2) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } O_1=O_2 \text{ and } V_1=V_2 \text{ Z-deviation.} \\ \frac{|V_1-V_2|}{\text{Range}(\text{Dom}(A_1))} & \text{if } O_1=O_2 \text{ and } V_1 \neq V_2 \text{ V-deviation} \\ \text{opdist}(O_1, O_2)/5 & \text{if } O_1 \neq O_2 \text{ and } V_1=V_2 \text{ C-deviation.} \\ f(c,v) & \text{if } O_1 \neq O_2 \text{ and } V_1 \neq V_2 \text{ CV-deviation.} \end{cases}$$

Lemma 3.1. The conjunct level deviation lies between $[0,1]$

Proof 3.1. By definitions 3.2 and 3.3.

It is easy to see that:

- $\delta(c_i, c_j) \geq 0$,
- $\delta(c_i, c_i) = 0$,
- $\delta(c_i, c_j) = \delta(c_j, c_i)$.

However, $\delta(c_i, c_j)$ does not satisfy triangular inequality in case of CV-deviation, where we capture user subjectivity.

C. Conjunct Set Deviation

In order to compute novelty index of a rule, it is necessary to define the deviation Ψ between two conjunct sets, since both antecedents and consequents are considered to be sets of conjuncts. The deviation $\Psi(S_1, S_2)$ between two conjunct sets is quantified based on the analysis of the possible types of differences between two sets of conjuncts S_1 and S_2 . Without loss of generalization, we assume that an attribute occurs at most once in a conjunct set S . Computation of deviation at this level is based on counting incompatible conjuncts among the two sets and quantifying total deviation among the compatible conjuncts. Intuitively, it is the number of incompatible conjuncts that contribute most towards the value of the deviation. While comparing two sets of conjuncts namely S_1 and S_2 , three possibilities arise.

- S_1 and S_2 are identical.
- S_1 is a generalization / specialization of S_2 .
- S_1 and S_2 are different.

In case 1, the deviation must be nil, while in case 2, it is desirable to quantify the degree of generalization / specialization. In case 3, the degree of novelty is decided on the basis of deviation between the two sets needs to be quantified.

We compute the deviation between two conjunct sets as follows.

Definition 3.4 Let S_1 and S_2 be two conjunct sets with cardinalities $|S_1|$ and $|S_2|$ respectively. Let k be the pairs of compatible conjuncts between S_1 and S_2 . The deviation between S_1 and S_2 is computed as:

$$\Psi(S_1, S_2) = \frac{\{|S_1| + |S_2| - 2 * k\} + \sum_{i=1}^k \delta(c_1^i, c_2^i)}{|S_1| + |S_2|}$$

where (c_1^i, c_2^i) is the i^{th} pair of compatible conjuncts.

Theorem 3.1 For any two conjunct sets S_1 and S_2 ,

$$0 \leq \Psi(S_1, S_2) \leq 1.$$

Proof 3.1 The proof follows by simple reasoning. We consider two extreme cases where there are no compatible conjuncts and another with all equal conjuncts.

In case there are no compatible conjuncts, $k=0$ and the second component of the numerator vanishes. With all non-compatible conjuncts, $\Psi(S_1, S_2)=1$. In case the two conjunct sets are equal, $k = \frac{|S_1| + |S_2|}{2}$ and the second component in the

numerator reduces to zero. Thus $\Psi(S_1, S_2) = 0$, which captures Z-deviation.

Note that

- i) $\Psi(S_1, S_2) \geq 0$,
- ii) $\Psi(S_1, S_1) = 0$, and
- iii) $\Psi(S_1, S_2) = \Psi(S_2, S_1)$.

We do not expect Ψ to satisfy triangular inequality in view of its violation by underlying conjunct level deviation function. Therefore, Ψ can't be used as a distance metric.

Example 1

Given two conjunct sets S_1 and S_2 as follows:

$$S_1 = \{C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4, C_5\}$$

$$S_2 = \{C_1, C_2\}$$

The deviation of S_2 with respect to S_1 is computed according to definition 3.4 as follows:

$$\Psi(S_1, S_2) = \frac{|5| + |2| - 2 * 2 + 0}{|5| + |2|} = \frac{3}{7} = 0.42$$

Note that S_1 is specialization of S_2 , and hence, the deviation of S_1 with respect to S_2 also indicates the degree of specialization. Similarly, $\Psi(S_2, S_1) = 0.42$ also indicates the degree of generalization of S_2 with respect to S_1 .

Although the deviation between two conjunct sets in case of specialization / generalization can be interpreted as degree of specialization / generalization as shown in Example 1, the interpretation is not natural. Intuitively, the degree of specialization (generalization) of S_1 (S_2) with respect to S_2 (S_1) should reflect the ratio of extra (i.e. newly added) conjuncts to the total number of conjuncts in the specialized (generalized) rule.

For this reason, we propose an alternative approach which computes the deviation of specialization / generalization in the next section. However, use of Definition 3.4 for computation of degree of imparts uniformity and mathematical elegance.

D. Generalization and Specialization

Before computing $\Psi(S_1, S_2)$ for two conjunct sets S_1 and S_2 , it is necessary to check for generalization or specialization between them. If one of the sets is completely subsumed by the other, then this is a case for *GS* deviation. In this case it is necessary to compute the degree of generalization or specialization to enable the end-user judge the degree of novelty.

Definition 3.5 Let S_1 and S_2 be two conjunct sets such that S_1 is completely subsumed by the S_2 . Then S_1 is generalization of S_2 and the deviation (degree of generalization) is given by:

$$\Psi(S_1, S_2) = \frac{|S_2| - |C|}{|S_2|}$$

where C is the set of subsumed conjuncts.

Definition 3.6 Let S_1 and S_2 be two conjunct sets such that S_2 is completely subsumed by S_1 . Then S_1 is specialization of S_2 and the deviation (degree of specialization) is given by:

$$\Psi(S_1, S_2) = \frac{|S_1| - |C|}{|S_1|}$$

where C is the set of subsumed conjuncts.

Note that high magnitude of generalization / specialization indicates high degree of novelty.

Example 2

Given two conjunct sets S_1 and S_2 as follows:

$$S_1 = \{C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4, C_5\}$$

$$S_2 = \{C_1, C_2\}$$

The deviation (degree of *specialization*) of S_1 with respect to S_2 is computed according to Definition 3.6 as follows:

$$\Psi(S_1, S_2) = \frac{|5| - |2|}{5} = \frac{3}{5} = 0.6$$

Similarly, in case of deviation (degree of *generalization*) of S_1 with respect to S_2 is computed according to Definition 3.5 is 0.6.

Note that the computations in Example 2 are closer to the intuitive notion of the deviation compared to those of Example 1.

IV. COMPUTING NOVELTY INDEX

Novelty index of a rule r is defined with respect to a given rule set R . It is computed as paired deviation of antecedent and consequent of r relative to the closest rule in R . The rule $s \in R$, from whose antecedent the deviation of r is minimum is considered to be closest. The novelty index is defined as follows.

Definition 3.7 Let $r: A_r \rightarrow C_r$ be a rule whose *novelty index* is to be computed with respect to the rule set R . Then

$$N_r^R = (\min_{s \in R} (\Psi(A_r, A_s), \Psi(C_r, C_s)))$$
 gives the *novelty index*.

Having computed the *novelty index* for all the rules in the currently discovered rule set with respect to previously discovered rule set, the task of rule reduction can be performed in several ways. Some of the suggested ways are:

- i) select the top K novel rules,
- ii) select rules with novelty index exceeding a threshold,
- iii) categorize the indexed rules as per Table I.

V. ALGORITHM

We give below the algorithm for categorizing rules in a give rule set R_{CDK} (currently discovered knowledge) with respect to the rule base R_{PDK} (previously discovered knowledge)

Input : Two rulesets R_{PDK} & R_{CDK}

Output: Updated R_{PDK} and a Tag for each rule in R_{CDK}

Process:

- For each $R_i (A_i \rightarrow C_i)$ in R_{CDK}
 - Find $R_j (A_j \rightarrow C_j)$ from R_{PDK} , such that $\Psi(A_i, A_j)$ is minimum.
 - Compute $\Psi(C_i, C_j)$
 - Categorize R_i as per Table I.
 - If category is **Novel**, add to R_{PDK} .

Categorization	Semantics	Condition
Conforming Rules	Rules that have been discovered earlier.	$\check{A} \leq \Phi$ & $\check{C} \leq \Phi$
Generalized (Specialized) Rules	Rules that are generalization (specialization) of some earlier discovered rules.	$A_r(A_s)$ subsumes $A_s(A_r)$ & $\check{C} = 0$
Unexpected Rules	Rules that are unexpectedly different from the previously discovered rules.	$\check{A} \leq \Phi$ & $\check{C} \geq \Phi$ OR $\check{A} \geq \Phi$ & $\check{C} \leq \Phi$
Novel Rules	Rules that add to knowledge. Such rules do not fall into any of the earlier specified categories.	$\check{A} \geq \Phi$ & $\check{C} \geq \Phi$

Where ($\check{A} = \Psi(A_i, A_j)$ & $\check{C} = \Psi(C_i, C_j)$) & Φ is a user specified threshold).

VI. EXAMPLE

For better understanding of our framework, we present an example from the 'supmart' dataset available in CBA [20]. The following set of rules was discovered by CBA at time T_1 , and we designate this as currently discovered knowledge. We consider the previously discovered knowledge to be null at T_1 .

- R_1 : potato chips = Y ^ ketchup = Y → beer = Y ^ orange juice = Y
- R_2 : orange juice = Y ^ ketchup = Y → beer = Y ^ potato chips = Y
- R_3 : sugar = Y ^ potato chips = Y ^ orange juice = Y → ketchup = Y
- R_4 : sugar = Y ^ potato chips = Y ^ ketchup = Y → orange juice = Y
- R_5 : sugar = Y ^ orange juice = Y ^ ketchup = Y → potato chips = Y
- R_6 : potato chips = Y ^ orange juice = Y ^ ketchup = Y → sugar = Y
- R_7 : sugar = Y ^ potato chips = Y → orange juice = Y ^ ketchup = Y
- R_8 : sugar = Y ^ orange juice = Y → potato chips = Y ^ ketchup = Y
- R_9 : potato chips = Y ^ orange juice = Y → sugar = Y ^ ketchup = Y
- R_{10} : beer = Y ^ orange juice = Y ^ ketchup = Y → sugar = Y

If the user specifies $w_1 = 0.4$, $w_2 = 0.6$ for CV-deviation and $\Phi = 0.5$, the novelty index assigned to rules discovered at time T_1 given below in the format:

Rule: {Closest Rule, [\check{A} , \check{C}], Category}.

- R_1 : {-, [1,1], Novel}, R_2 : { R_1 , [0.5,0.5], Conformed}
- R_3 : { R_1 , [0.6,1], Novel}, R_4 : { R_1 , [0.2,0.3], Conformed}
- R_5 : { R_3 , [0.3,1], Unexpected}, R_6 : { R_1 , [0.2,1], Unexpected}
- R_7 : { R_3 , [0.2,0.3], Conformed}, R_8 : { R_3 , [0.2,0.3], Conformed}
- R_9 : { R_3 , [0.2,0.3], Conformed}, R_{10} : { R_1 , [0.6,1], Novel}

Now, previously discovered knowledge consists of ruleset $R_{PDK} = \{R_1, R_3, R_{10}\}$

The following rules are discovered latter at time T_2 (R_{CDK}):

- R_{11} : orange juice = Y ^ ketchup = Y → sugar = Y
- R_{12} : ketchup = Y → sugar = Y ^ orange juice = Y
- R_{13} : ketchup = Y → tomato sauce = Y
- R_{14} : potato chips = Y ^ tomato sauce = Y → ketchup = Y
- R_{15} : potato chips = Y ^ ketchup = Y → tomato sauce = Y
- R_{16} : tomato sauce = Y ^ ketchup = Y → potato chips = Y

- R_{17} : potato chips = Y → tomato sauce = Y ^ ketchup = Y
- R_{18} : ketchup = Y → potato chips = Y ^ tomato sauce = Y
- R_{19} : beer = Y ^ potato chips = Y ^ tomato sauce = Y → ketchup = Y
- R_{20} : beer = Y ^ potato chips = Y ^ ketchup = Y → tomato sauce = Y

Categorizing this ruleset with respect to R, we get:

- R_{11} : { R_{10} , [0.3,0], Generalized}, R_{12} : { R_1 , [0.3,0.5], Conformed}
- R_{13} : { R_1 , [0.3,1], Unexpected}, R_{14} : { R_1 , [0.5,1], Unexpected}
- R_{15} : { R_1 , [0,1], Unexpected}, R_{16} : { R_1 , [0.5,1], Unexpected}
- R_{17} : { R_1 , [0.3,1], Unexpected}, R_{18} : { R_1 , [0.3,1], Unexpected}
- R_{19} : { R_1 , [0.6,1], Novel}, R_{20} : { R_1 , [0.2,1], Unexpected}

R_{PDK} is now updated to { R_1, R_3, R_{10}, R_{19} }

VII. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

The proposed approach is implemented in C language and tested using public datasets available in [19]. Since, there are no other approaches available, which objectively quantify novelty and yet take user subjectivity into account; we could not perform any comparison against our approach. The following experiments were conducted to show the effectiveness of the framework:

A. Experiment One

We worked with five public datasets available at [19]. We considered each of these datasets as evolving with time, and partitioned them into 3 increments: D_1 , D_2 and D_3 mined at times T_1 , T_2 and T_3 respectively. We took each of these partitions to be equal for purpose of generating rules.

The datasets were mined, using CBA [20], with 0.1% and 1% as minimum confidence and support respectively, uniformly for all datasets. The low thresholds enable generation of large number of rules; thereby demonstrating the efficiency of the framework. The discovered rules were categorized as in Table I, with $\Phi = 0.5$ and $f(c,v) \rightarrow [0.4,0.6]$ for CV-deviation. Table II summarizes the result.

TABLE II
DISCOVERED RULES AT TIME T_1 , T_2 AND T_3 FOR DIFFERENT DATASETS WITH $\Phi = 0.5$

Dataset	Time	Instances	Discovered rules	Novel	Unexpected	Specialized	Generalized	Conformed
Census	T_1	12000	942	29	239	4	19	652
	T_2	12000	1061	6	189	20	21	825
	T_3	8561	636	3	58	8	7	560
Supmart	T_1	40	2775	25	1576	62	75	1025
	T_2	40	1875	0	1026	49	103	661
	T_3	48	1570	0	717	40	116	697
German	T_1	333	117	13	66	0	0	38
	T_2	333	118	9	43	0	0	66
	T_3	334	133	4	56	3	1	69
Sick	T_1	933	29	4	18	0	1	6
	T_2	933	33	2	17	7	0	7
	T_3	934	32	2	16	5	1	8
Heart	T_1	90	38	7	5	24	0	2
	T_2	90	95	6	6	71	2	10
	T_3	90	40	2	4	19	2	13

B. Experiment Two

The second experiment was performed using 'census' dataset to study the effect of novelty threshold Φ on the number of rules of different categories. This dataset contains 48842 instances, mix of continuous and discrete attributes, and 2 class values. With same partitions (12000,12000,8561) and support and confidence thresholds as in the previous experiment. The number of rules varied as per our expectation. The result is shown in Table III.

TABLE III
 DISCOVERED RULES AT TIME T_1 , T_2 AND T_3 FOR DIFFERENT (Φ)

Novelty Degree (Φ)	Time	Discovered rules	Novel	Unexpected	Specialized	Generalized	Conformed
$\Phi=0.9$	T_1	942	4	318	0	2	618
	T_2	1061	0	451	5	2	603
	T_3	636	0	241	6	1	388
$\Phi=0.8$	T_1	942	6	241	1	4	690
	T_2	1061	1	235	1	2	822
	T_3	636	0	130	4	1	501
$\Phi=0.7$	T_1	942	10	325	1	5	601
	T_2	1061	2	314	4	6	735
	T_3	636	0	164	5	2	465
$\Phi=0.6$	T_1	942	16	227	15	11	673
	T_2	1061	7	135	16	16	887
	T_3	636	1	79	16	9	531
$\Phi=0.5$	T_1	942	29	239	4	19	652
	T_2	1061	6	189	20	21	825
	T_3	636	3	58	8	7	560
$\Phi=0.4$	T_1	942	49	439	7	27	420
	T_2	1061	20	306	36	36	663
	T_3	636	8	114	29	15	470
$\Phi=0.3$	T_1	942	62	593	5	27	255
	T_2	1061	25	629	39	34	334
	T_3	636	15	268	25	24	304

VIII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we proposed a strategy for rule set reduction based on the *Novelty index* of the rule. *Novelty index* of a newly discovered rule is the quantification of its deviation with respect to the known rule set. The quantification is objective and based on assumption of additive nature of newness. User subjectivity is captured by specification of threshold(s) for rule categorization.

The framework is implemented and evaluated using synthetic and real-life datasets and has shown positive results. The generated rules were categorized as conforming, generalized/specialized, unexpected and novel rules.

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